

METHODOLOGY FOR MULTI-CRITERIA OPTIMISATION OF CO₂ TRANSPORT FOR VARIOUS MODES OF CO₂ TRANSPORT

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D4.6 Methodology for multi-criteria optimisation of CO₂ transport for various modes of CO₂ transport

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The accelerated uptake of Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS), needed to reach the net zero emission target by 2050, will critically depend on the success of least-cost environmentally benign & efficient CO₂ capture technologies to be demonstrated at full commercial scale by 2030. Rising to the above challenge, CaLby2030 focuses on TRL6 demonstration of its pioneering Calcium Looping (CaL) CO₂ capture systems using the well-established Circulating Fluidised Bed (CFB) technology to a state ready for large-scale commercial deployment in key high-emitting industries by 2030. Importantly, the deployment of the CFB-CaL capture technologies in the CCUS industrial clusters requires the design of safe and economic solutions for CO₂ transport. In CaLby2030 project, advanced modelling tools are developed to optimise the CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure solutions for the CCUS clusters.

This report is focused on developing a methodology for designing cost-effective, safe, and sustainable multi-modal CO₂ transport solutions utilising pipelines, trucks, rail, and ships, to suit different phases of CCUS deployment in large-scale and also small-scale cluster projects in various geographical regions. The report outlines the methodology for optimizing the CO₂ transport chains, using a bi-level optimization approach. The first step employs Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) to minimize the transportation costs, considering the CO₂ volumes, the CO₂ sources and storage locations, and the presence of existing transport routes and suitable infrastructure. The second step involves using a multi-criteria optimization to balance the costs and the environmental and safety impacts for a number of CO₂ transport solutions obtained in the MILP step.

The MILP model has been tested for simple scenario cases, while the multi-objective optimisation model was applied to assess shipping and pipeline CO₂ transport solutions in a realistic CCS cluster, based on the economic and environmental criteria.

The developed methodology offers a comprehensive approach to addressing the economic, environmental, and safety challenges of CO₂ transportation, paving the way for more effective CCUS deployment. The methodology will be employed to optimise CO₂ transport solutions for the CaLby2030 demonstration plants in WP5, leading to deliverable D5.5.

2 INTRODUCTION

Given the urgent requirement for CO₂ emission reduction at all levels, Carbon Capture and Sequestration (CCS) is believed to hold a key role in industrial decarbonisation. However, the design and deployment of an efficient infrastructure for economical, safe, reliable and sustainable transport of CO₂ from industrial emitters to geological storage locations presents a major barrier to CCS implementation (Fraga, et al., 2021).

Indeed, transportation of the captured CO₂ accounts for an important portion of the overall costs of the CCS chain. The CO₂ can be either compressed and transported via pipelines in gaseous phase (ca. 25-40 bar) or dense phase (ca. 90-120 bar), or liquefied and transported via containers at pressures and temperatures ranging from 7 bar and -50 °C to 20 bar and -30 °C, depending on the design of the vessel (IPCC). While food grade CO₂ has been transported

via modular vessels as a valuable product for decades, it would be too costly for large-scale deployment of CCS. Given different amounts of CO₂ that would require transport in different stages and different parts of CCS projects applied to industrial clusters and geographical regions, further analysis and optimisation of the transportation chains are required to determine optimal CO₂ transport solutions.

In large-scale projects, the CO₂ is primarily transported via pipelines and ships where the costs vary significantly, depending on scale and distances (ZEP, 2011). The deployment of CCS technologies in the near future, will entail the capture from small emitters (<100 kt_{CO2}/y), for which other modes of transport, such as trucks and rail, can be more economical and faster to implement (Oeuvray, 2022). The combination of different modes of CO₂ transport also, in many cases, can represent a better alternative to a single mode of transportation.

Costs are, however, not the only obstacle to the large-scale implementation of CCS. From a societal perspective, the optimal design of multi-modal CO₂ transport infrastructure for utilization and storage involves a cost-benefit analysis with the aim of minimizing not only costs, but also environmental impact and reducing the safety risks associated with failure of elements of the infrastructure.

Resolving these complex challenges requires developing models and tools to balance the key impact factors when designing CO₂ transport networks. Given that every specific CO₂ transport project has its own unique features and design constraints, the modelling tool must be flexible, able to handle several factors, such as the amount of CO₂ to be transported, locations of the source and the storage site, existing infrastructure, cost of fuels and electricity, sustainability metrics, safety features and more. This report describes the methodology constructed in the project to perform multi-criteria optimization of multi-modal CO₂ transport chains for CCS.

3 OUTLINE OF THE METHODOLOGY

The work proposed in this deliverable entails the development of a number of independent modelling tools, aimed at optimization of a CO₂ transport infrastructure for a generic Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS) project involving multiple geographically distributed CO₂ sources and storage locations. The methodology uses a bi-level optimization, where the first step involves using a linear programming method to obtain cost-optimal CO₂ transport infrastructure designs satisfying the specified project constraints, and evaluating the infrastructure environmental and safety impacts for these solutions. In the second step, a multi-criteria optimization tool aggregating the cost, environmental and risk criteria is applied to determine the optimal multi-modal transport solution for the project. The overall approach and methodology is briefly introduced in this section, while a more detailed description of each individual tool is given in the following chapters.

3.1 Step 1. Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP): Minimizing the Cost of Transport

In this step, a MILP approach is applied to optimize CO₂ transport for the CCUS project subject to a number of system conditions and constraints (as detailed in CHAPTER 3). These may include the geographical locations of the emitters and the utilization sites, the availability or accessibility of routes and infrastructure for different modes of transport, along with the respective amounts of CO₂ and the relevant temperature and pressure conditions. Established techno-economic models are employed to determine the CO₂ transport and conditioning unit costs for the various transport modes, such as pipelines (Knoope, et al., 2014), ships (EE, 2018; Roussanaly, et al., 2021), and trucks (Stolaroff, et al., 2021). The MILP solutions are then obtained for a specified range of costs that are considered reasonable. Figure 1

illustrates the proposed methodology, where the MILP results include three solutions for CO₂ transport chains involving different combinations via different transport modes.

FIGURE 1 Diagram showing the MILP input data and the results of optimization of the multi-modal transport of CO₂.

3.2 Step 2. Multi-Modal Transport of CO₂: Incorporating Safety and Environmental Impact Costs

For step 2, models are developed to calculate an Environmental Index (CHAPTER 4) and a Safety Index (CHAPTER 5) for the different modes of CO₂ transportation, adopting approaches and findings from the previous studies on transportation of either CO₂ or H₂ (Bevrani, et al., 2020) (d'Amore, et al., 2018); (Lee, et al., 2017); (Kim, et al., 2011). The Safety Index considers factors such as failure rates, and incorporates elements of the consequence analysis of failure, which takes into account the population density along the selected route. The Environmental Index, on the other hand, describes the impact of CO₂ emissions associated with the construction and implementation of the different modes of transport, accounting for the transportation distance along the selected routes.

In the developed multi-criteria optimization model, the trade-offs between the economic cost, risk and environmental impact of the transport solutions returned by the MILP are evaluated to determine the most optimal solution or solutions, as illustrated in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 Illustration of the process and parameters involved in applying the multi-criteria optimization model.

4 MIXED INTEGER LINEAR PROGRAMMING (MILP) MODEL

The MILP optimization is particularly useful for decision-making problems where both discrete and continuous decisions need to be decided simultaneously. Discrete decisions involve choices that can only take on specific, distinct values, such as selecting whether or not to build a facility or determining the number of transportation routes to establish. Continuous decisions, on the other hand, involve variables that can take on any value within a given range, such as the amount of CO₂ to be transported through a pipeline. The general form of MILP is written as

$$\min_x (p^T x) \quad (1)$$

subject to

$$A \cdot x \leq b \quad (2)$$

$$A_{eq} \cdot x = b_{eq} \quad (3)$$

$$lb \leq x \leq ub \quad (4)$$

where p is the vector of objective functions, and x is the column vector of unknowns that include real variables, representing, e.g., the transportation distance between the nodes, and the integer “binary variables”, implementing the model constraints. Eqs. (2)–(4) describe the model additional constraints due to the nature of the problem and limits on the variables. The MILP problem typically consists of input data, decision variables, linear inequality constraints, and an objective function.

The optimal design of CO₂ transportation network is determined by solving the MILP optimization problem that minimizes the total cost of the infrastructure construction and operation for a finite set of CO₂ transportation modes and the system-specific conditions and constraints. The “conditions” refer to the particular characteristics and requirements of the CO₂ transport system, such as the geographical layout, the types of CO₂ transportation, and the emissions at various locations. “Constraints” are the limitations or rules that must be adhered to, such as capacity limits of pipelines, and connection rules that restrict how the CO₂ can be transported.

4.1 The model assumptions and compact notation

Figure 3 shows a geographical region where the sets of CO₂ industrial emitters N_c , geological sequestration sites N_s and interim storage locations N_b are to be connected via different CO₂ transport modes. The arrows show schematically the connections and direction of CO₂ transport between the nodes using dedicated transport modes, selected from a given set of modes, Y , including pipeline, truck, train, and ship, represented by different colors. The total set of the network nodes, N , combines the sets N_c , N_b and N_s , and can be expanded to include additional interim nodes resolving the geographical transportation routes.

FIGURE 3 An example of geographical locations of CO₂ industrial emitters (the circles scaled according to the CO₂ emission rates), the interim storage and the geological storage sites, all representing the nodes in the MILP model. The arrows show the potential connections between the nodes.

In Figure 3, the circles represent the locations of onshore emission sources, with larger circles indicating higher emission volumes. The interim storage ports provide the link between the onshore transport network and the CO₂ storage site. Shipping is assumed as the mode of transport between the ports and the storage site.

We included seven common modes of transportation, including pipelines transporting CO₂ in gas phase and dense phase, trucks and ships transporting cryogenic liquid CO₂ at low and high pressures, and trains transporting CO₂ in liquid phase. Given the different operating temperature and pressure conditions used in the different CO₂ transportation modes, our model includes not only the transportation costs but also the CO₂ conditioning costs when transferring CO₂ from one mode to another. This is typically a significant expense in multimodal transportation that should not be overlooked.

4.2 Input data

The input data is the data or constants that are known before solving the MILP problem. The input data for the MILP model consists of:

- (i) the locations and rates CO₂ emissions from the plants;
- (ii) the locations and capacities of CO₂ storage sites;
- (iii) the costs of transportation, conditioning and interim storage;
- (iv) the availability of CO₂ transportation modes (i.e., the connectivity between nodes).

All the model input data are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Inputs for MILP.

The variable description	Variable	Units	The variable ranges
Nodes sets	\mathbf{N}	-	$\begin{cases} \mathbf{N}_c : \text{Emitter nodes} \\ \mathbf{N}_b : \text{Interim storage nodes} \\ \mathbf{N}_s : \text{Final storage nodes} \\ \mathbf{N} = \mathbf{N}_c \cup \mathbf{N}_b \cup \mathbf{N}_s \end{cases}$
Node number	i	-	$\forall i \in \mathbf{N}$
CO ₂ emission at emitters	E_i	Mt/yr	$\forall i \in \mathbf{N}_c$
Capacity of interim storage	P_i	Mt/yr	$\forall i \in \mathbf{N}_b$
Capacity of storage sites	S_i	Mt/yr	$\forall i \in \mathbf{N}_s$
Transport mode	$y \in \mathbf{Y}$	-	$\begin{cases} \mathbf{Y} = \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_7\} \\ y_1 = 1 : \text{pipeline_gas} \\ y_2 = 2 : \text{pipeline_dense} \\ y_3 = 3 : \text{truck_low pressure} \\ y_4 = 4 : \text{truck_high pressure} \\ y_5 = 5 : \text{train} \\ y_6 = 6 : \text{ship_low pressure} \\ y_7 = 7 : \text{ship_high pressure} \end{cases}$
Logical variable describing the feasibility of CO ₂ transport mode y between the nodes i and i'	$w_{i,i',y} \in \{0,1\}$	-	$\forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}, \forall y \in \mathbf{Y}$
Nodes location – latitude	ϕ_i	-	$\forall i \in \mathbf{N}$
Nodes location – longitude	λ_i	-	$\forall i \in \mathbf{N}$
Distance between the nodes i and i'	$L_{i,i',y}$	km	$\forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}, \forall y \in \mathbf{Y}$
Unit annual CAPEX for the transport mode y	α_y	€/(tCO ₂ ·km)	$\forall y \in \mathbf{Y}, \alpha_y = [\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_7]_{1 \times 7}$
Unit annual OPEX for the transport mode y	β_y	€/(tCO ₂ ·km)	$\forall y \in \mathbf{Y}, \beta_y = [\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_7]_{1 \times 7}$

Unit annual conditioning CAPEX from y to y'	$\mathbf{f}_{y,y'}$	€/tCO ₂	$\forall y, y' \in \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{f}_{y,y'} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & f_{1,2} & \cdots & f_{1,7} \\ f_{2,1} & 0 & \cdots & f_{2,7} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f_{7,1} & f_{7,2} & \cdots & 0 \end{bmatrix}_{7 \times 7}$
Unit annual conditioning OPEX from y to y'	$\mathbf{g}_{y,y'}$	€/tCO ₂	$\forall y, y' \in \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{g}_{y,y'} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & g_{1,2} & \cdots & g_{1,7} \\ g_{2,1} & 0 & \cdots & g_{2,7} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ g_{7,1} & g_{7,2} & \cdots & 0 \end{bmatrix}_{7 \times 7}$
Unit CO ₂ emission during transportation y	e_y	tCO ₂ /(tCO ₂ ·km)	$\forall y \in \mathbf{Y}$
Unit CO ₂ emission for conditioning from y to y'	$\mathbf{m}_{y,y'}$	tCO ₂ /tCO ₂	$\forall y, y' \in \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{m}_{y,y'} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & m_{1,2} & \cdots & m_{1,7} \\ m_{2,1} & 0 & \cdots & m_{2,7} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ m_{7,1} & m_{7,2} & \cdots & 0 \end{bmatrix}_{7 \times 7}$

The above subscript “ i, i' ” refers to CO₂ transport from node i to node i' .

4.3 Decision variables

The decision variables represent the unknowns of the MILP model. Table 2 lists the decision variables for the model.

Table 2. The MILP decision variables.

The variable description	Variable	Units	The variable ranges
Logical variable for the implementation status of the transport mode y between nodes i and i'	$c_{i,i',y} \in \{0,1\}$	-	$\forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}, \forall y \in \mathbf{Y}$
Design capacity of the transport mode y between nodes i and i'	$R_{i,i',y} \in \mathbb{R}$	tCO ₂	$\forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}, \forall y \in \mathbf{Y}$
Flowrate of CO ₂ using the transport mode y between nodes i and i'	$G_{i,i',y} \in \mathbb{R}$	tCO ₂	$\forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}, \forall y \in \mathbf{Y}$
Logical variable for the installation status of CO ₂ transport mode y between nodes i and i'	$z_{i,i',y} \in \{0,1\}$	-	$\forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}, \forall y \in \mathbf{Y}$
CO ₂ stored at interim nodes	$B_i \in \mathbb{R}$	tCO ₂	$\forall i \in \mathbf{N}_b$
CO ₂ stored at storage sites	$U_i \in \mathbb{R}$	tCO ₂	$\forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}_s$

4.4 Constraints

The constraints are the conditions that the decision variables must satisfy for the solution to be feasible—to meet the real limitations and respect all necessary requirements for the network. These include CO₂ mass balance, limitations on transportation capacity, connection requirements, maximum or minimum flow rates, and storage capacities.

4.4.1 CO₂ mass balance

For each node n_i of the network (see Fig. 1) the CO₂ mass balance is expressed as

$$\sum_{y \in \mathbf{Y}} \sum_{\substack{i' \in \mathbf{N} \\ i' \neq i}} (G_{i',i,y} - G_{i,i',y}) + E_i - B_i = U_i \cdot \quad (5)$$

Considering the difference between the node subsets, Eq. (2) has following constraints:

$$\begin{cases} B_i = 0, U_i = 0 & \forall i \in \mathbf{N}_c \\ E_i = 0, B_i = 0, U_i = 0 & \forall i \in \mathbf{N}_b \\ E_i = 0, B_i = 0 & \forall i \in \mathbf{N}_s \\ \sum_{i \in \mathbf{N}_s} U_i = \sum_{i \in \mathbf{N}_c} E_i \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

4.4.2 Constitutive equations for transportation

Eq. (7) is the constitutive equation of transportation. The flowrate is constrained by the installed capacity of CO₂ transport solution on the route connecting nodes i and i' , while the possibility of installation transport technology is constrained by the feasibility of the corresponding connections:

$$c_{i,i',y} R_{i,i',y}^{\min} \leq R_{i,i',y} \leq c_{i,i',y} R_{i,i',y}^{\max} \quad (7)$$

where $c_{i,i',y} \leq w_{i,i',y}$, $R_{i,i',y}^{\min}$ and $R_{i,i',y}^{\max}$ are the minimum and maximum available values for the connection, respectively.

The CO₂ flow rate for any connection route is constrained by the installed transport capacity:

$$G_{i,i',y} \leq z_{i,i',y} R_{i,i',y} \cdot \quad (8)$$

4.4.3 Other constraints

Other constraints describe the proper connections of the nodes. Here the following rules are applied: Only one transport mode can be used between any two nodes:

$$\sum_y z_{i,i',y} \leq 1, \quad \forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}, i \neq i'. \quad (9)$$

There is no bi-directional transportation between any two directly connected nodes:

$$\sum_y (z_{i,i',y} + z_{i',i,y}) \leq 1, \quad \forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}, i \neq i'. \quad (10)$$

CO₂ streams can only be combined rather than split at any node:

$$\sum_{i'} z_{i,i',y} \leq 1, \quad \forall i, i' \in \mathbf{N}, i \neq i'. \quad (11)$$

Among the three interim storage nodes (at the locations of the three ports), only one node can be chosen, and there is no transportation between any two ports. CO₂ from the port, can be transported only to the storage site:

$$\sum_{y \in \{y_6, y_7\}} \sum_{i \in \mathbf{N}_b} z_{i,i',y} = 1, \quad i' \in \mathbf{N}_s. \quad (12)$$

4.5 Objective function

The objective function defines the variable that the MILP model aims to minimize or maximize. In the context of CO₂ transportation, the objective function represents the total cost, which includes both transportation and conditioning costs. The objective function guides the optimization process by defining what constitutes the best solution, for example cost-efficiency.

The transportation cost is calculated as the sum of the CAPEX and OPEX.

The total CAPEX for the transportation (TCAPTRA) is expressed as the sum of CAPEX for all the segments of the CO₂ transport network:

$$\text{TCAPTRA} = \sum_i \sum_{i'} \sum_y R_{i,i',y} \cdot L_{i,i'} \cdot \alpha_y. \quad (13)$$

Similarly, the total OPEX for the transportation (TOPTRA) is defined as:

$$\text{TOPTRA} = \sum_i \sum_{i'} \sum_y G_{i,i',y} \cdot L_{i,i'} \cdot \beta_y. \quad (14)$$

The conditioning cost is calculated depending on the difference between the upstream pressure and downstream pressures at node i . In order to select the correct unit conditioning cost from matrices $\mathbf{f}_{y,y'}$ and $\mathbf{g}_{y,y'}$ based on the upstream and downstream, a logical variable $z_{\text{out},i}$ is introduced:

$$z_{\text{out},i} = \frac{\sum_{i'} \sum_y (G_{i,i',y} - G_{i',i,y})}{\sqrt{\left| \sum_{i'} \sum_y (G_{i,i',y} - G_{i',i,y}) \right|^2}}. \quad (15)$$

Then, the total CAPEX for conditioning is calculated as

$$\text{TCAPCOND} = \sum_i \mathbf{z}_{\text{out},i} \cdot \mathbf{f}'_{y,y'} \cdot \left[\sum_{i'} \sum_y (G_{i,i',y} - G_{i',i,y})' \right]. \quad (16)$$

where the prime (') represents the transpose for the matrix, and the term $(G_{i,i',y} - G_{i',i,y})$ describes the net flow rate at node i .

The total OPEX for conditioning is defined as

$$\text{TOPCOND} = \sum_i \mathbf{z}_{\text{out},i} \cdot \mathbf{g}'_{y,y'} \cdot \left[\sum_{i'} \sum_y (G_{i,i',y} - G_{i',i,y})' \right]. \quad (17)$$

In addition, although the available data on liquefaction of pure CO₂ have been used for the preliminary cost estimations in $\mathbf{f}_{y,y'}$ and $\mathbf{g}_{y,y'}$, an in-house ASPEN Plus® model of the liquefaction process is being developed to enable more accurate estimation of the liquefaction costs of CO₂ originating from the different industries relevant to the project (see Table 3). The composition of the incoming streams has been obtained in consultation with LEAP and a range of inlet conditions (pre-compressed CO₂ at 120 bars for dense phase transport or 25-30 bars for gas phase

transport, and using CO₂ directly from capture process at 2.5-3 bars) and delivery pressures (7-20 bars) were taken into consideration.

TABLE 3. Calculated cost of CO₂ liquefaction (US\$) at the interface between gas phase and liquid phase CO₂ transport.

The matching modes of CO ₂ transport	IREN WtE		HUNOSA Bio-CHP		THOMAS ZEMENT		ALLEIMA Steel	
	CAPEX (M\$)	OPEX (M\$/yr)	CAPEX (M\$)	OPEX (M\$/yr)	CAPEX (M\$)	OPEX (M\$/yr)	CAPEX (M\$)	OPEX (M\$/yr)
Pipegas 30bar–Ship 15bar	7.59	2.40	8.11	2.58	1.54	6.75	10.52	4.38
Pipegas 30bar–Truck 19bar	6.33	2.04	6.84	2.22	13.92	6.23	9.14	4.01
Pipegas 30bar–Ship 7bar	8.03	2.48	8.39	2.71	16.63	7.78	11.83	5.02

The objective function of the MILP problem is the total cost of the system, including the capital cost and operation cost for transportation and conditioning for the whole system:

$$\text{COST} = \text{TCAPTRA} + \text{TOPTRA} + \text{TCAPCOND} + \text{TOPCOND} \quad (18)$$

The MILP optimization model, involving the minimization of the total costs defined by equation (15) complemented by the equality and inequality constraints defined in Section 3.4, was coded in MatLab for solution using the commercial solver Gurobi (Gurobi, 2021).

4.6 Model verification

To verify the model, two simple tests were designed for hypothetical scenarios where the optimal CO₂ transport solutions are predefined by the cheapest transport solutions for specific parts of the network. In these tests, relative costs were used rather than the real-world cost data. In both cases, we have set six emission sources in the geographical area of Germany, and one interim storage to be selected from three ports, five onshore transportation modes (y1 to y5), and two offshore transportation modes (y6 and y7).

For the case studied in Figure 4, we assigned y1 as the cheapest onshore transportation mode and y6 as the cheapest offshore transportation mode (0.5 €/tCO₂/km for y1 and y6, and 1 €/tCO₂/km for others). As it can be seen in Figure 4, the MILP model predicted the onshore transportation utilizing the cheapest mode, y1 (shown by red lines), and the offshore transport using the y6 mode (shown by yellow line). All the emission sources are rooted directly to the Hamburg port, rather than forming a series of connections with each other. This is because we set the unit price for y1 at 0.5 €/tCO₂/km annually, covering both CAPEX for new infrastructure and OPEX for operation. This setup implies

that any series connection with each other would result in a longer route to Hamburg, which is not the most economical solution under the given conditions.

FIGURE 4. Model verification for CO₂ transport network (No series connection).

In the second case study, we set y2 as the cheapest option at 0.5 €/km per year (0.5 €/km for y2 and y6, and 1 €/km for others). It's important to note that, for testing purposes, here this cost is per kilometer per year, independent of the transportation volume. Thus, the problem becomes a shortest path problem, where the goal is to connect all points using the shortest routes, without considering the flowrate of CO₂ at the emission sources. As shown in the Figure 5, with the exception of node 3, which is isolated due to its long distance to the other sources, all the other onshore nodes are connected along one route for transport of CO₂ using y2 mode (shown by green lines). This is the expected result, because CO₂ transport from the source nodes directly to the port (node 7) provides the lowest cost transport solution.

FIGURE 5. Model verification for CO₂ transport network (With series connection).

5 ENVIRONMENTAL INDEX

5.1 PRINCIPLES OF THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

In this study the environmental impact is calculated as the CO₂-equivalent emissions associated with CO₂ transportation. These include the direct emissions due to the use of fuels for road or marine transport and energy for conditioning (liquefaction and compression) as well as those derived by construction of the infrastructures, specifically linked to the amount of steel necessary to build ships, trucks, trains and pipelines. Other emission sources are also considered here, e.g., the CO₂ boil-off in ships, due to evaporation of the liquefied CO₂ in tanks because of the heat absorbed from the environment and the necessary release of a portion of the gas to avoid over-pressurization.

The CO₂ emissions are project specific and also depend on the transportation routes and the combination of modes employed. Here we propose an index which can be easily adapted to the specific requirements of the project, and can provide a valid tool for comparing different options. For each mode of CO₂ transportation, a set of data has been collected, either to be used as an input project-specific variable or as a parameter. The detailed description of the methodology follows in the next paragraph.

5.2 METHODOLOGY

The total emissions, T_{CO_2} (kg_{CO2}), for the selected configuration is calculated as

$$T_{CO_2} = \Sigma(C_a + U_a + C_{steel-a} + B_{off}) \quad (19)$$

where C_a (kg_{CO2}) are the emissions from fuels for mode a per leg of trip and is obtained for a specific multi-modal configuration as a sum of the contributions from the different vehicles, according to the type of fuel used and their consumption (Yang, et al., 2020); U_a (kg_{CO2}) are the emissions generated from the conditioning necessary to transport CO₂ via in mode a ; $C_{steel-a}$ (kg_{CO2}) is emissions due to steel making and it is based on the amount of steel necessary to construct the infrastructure for mode a ; B_{off} (kg_{CO2}) is the emission due to the boil off and it is only applicable to ships.

The terms in equation Eq. (19) are calculated using the following expressions:

$$C_a = \Sigma(X_{ab} P_b D_a) \quad (20)$$

$$P_b = M_b eP_b \quad (21)$$

where X_{ab} (kg_{fuel}/km) is the fuel consumption when transport mode a uses fuel type b (Table 4), P_b (kg_{CO2}/kg_{fuel}) is the emission coefficient of fuel b , M_b (TJ/Gg) is the net calorific value of fuel b ; eP_b (kg_{CO2}/TJ) is the carbon emission factor of fuel b , which is the emissions generating from burning 1 kg of fuel b and D_a is the distance travelled in mode a .

TABLE 4. Parameters settings for different fuels and modes of transportation.

Emissions from Fuel							
			Ship	Truck	Train	Notes	References
			MDO	Diesel	Diesel		
Carbon emission from mode a^1	C_a	kg _{CO2}	Equation 4.2			Depend on distance	(Yang, et al., 2020)
Fuel consumption when fuel type b is used by mode a	X_{ab}	kg _{fuel} /km	29.82	0.37	6.54	For ships a speed of 28 km/h is assumed	(EE, 2018); (Roussanaly, et al., 2021)
Carbon dioxide emission coefficient for fuel b	P_b	kg _{CO2} /kg _{fuel}	3.02	2.98	2.98		
Net calorific value of fuel b^1	M_b	TJ/Gg	28.2	43	43		(Yang, et al., 2020)
Carbon dioxide emission factor for fuel b^1	eP_b	kg _{CO2} /TJ	107000	69300	69300		(Yang, et al., 2020)
Density	d_e	kg/l	0.9	0.743	0.743		
Fuel consumption road ^{2,3}		l/km	-	0.5	8.8		(Karlsson, et al., 2023); (Talaiekhosani, et al., 2017)
Fuel consumption sea ³		t/h	0.835	-	-	Average for typical cargo ships	(Talaiekhosani, et al., 2017)

$$U_a = A_a E_a \quad (22)$$

where A_a represents the emission coefficient for the conditioning process associated to mode a (kg_{CO2}/kWh), e.g. liquefaction or compression, and E_a the energy used (kWh/t_{CO2}) which is project specific. The emission coefficient is dependent on the location and depends on the energy mix. For example, if the electricity comes from a grid with coal or natural gas, and renewables, the emission factor could be between 1 and 0.5 kg CO₂/kWh. If using renewables, this factor can be considerably lower, ranging from about 0.01 kg CO₂/kWh for wind power to 0.05 for solar, including emissions due to manufacturing, installation, and decommissioning (NREL, 2013):

$$C_{steel-a} = 1.8 Steel_a 1000/t_a \quad (23)$$

where the emissions are assumed as 1.8 tons of CO₂ per ton of steel produced from mode a and it is spread over the time of operation of the mode (t_a), and $Steel_a$ represents the amount of steel needed to construct the infrastructure and has been calculated based on general practice and literature data specific for each mode of transport. It depends on the capacity of the carrier (S_a), the transportation pressure, which determines the volume and the thickness of the tank, and additional structural steel. The amount of structural steel for ships was calculated using literature data on hull building procedures, which amounts to roughly 150% extra steel to add to the tank, while for trucks and trains 50% and 20% was used respectively:

$$B_{off} = hB_{off} CT_{ship} nT_{ship} \quad (24)$$

where hB_{off} is the hourly boil-off per ship, which is 0.15 % of the ship capacity; CT_{ship} is the total cruising time per fleet in hours generating the boil-off, calculated based on the distance travelled by each ship, the velocity (28 km/h) and the number of ships specific of the project; nT_{ship} is the number of trips per year.

6 SAFETY INDEX

6.1 RISK ASSESSMENT AND PRINCIPLES OF SAFETY INDEX DEVELOPMENT

To assess the risks associated to a given transportation option, a safety index is constructed here, which takes into consideration several risk factors unique to each mode of transportation. The latter include the probability of failure and the consequences of a hypothetical release, determined based on the results of calculations of dispersion of the CO₂ released from a fracture hole in a populated area:

$$\text{Safety Index} = \Sigma C_{x,y} \quad (25)$$

$$C_{x,y} = \Sigma(p_i * D_{i,y}) * PD_y * P_x * S \quad (26)$$

where y is the mode of transport (pipeline, truck, ship or rail); x is the failure mode, specific for the transport mode (Table 5); $C_{x,y}$ is the consequence of failure caused by the failure mode x for the transport mode y , $D_{i,y}$ is the dispersion area covered by the high-concentration CO₂ cloud released from the puncture hole i for transport mode y , and p_i is the probability of occurrence of a hole size i , while $\Sigma(p_i * D_{i,y})$ is the overall dispersion for mode y ; PD_y is the population density (often associated to the transport mode y as it can change depending on whether transport is on road or sea or via pipelines); P_x is the probability of failure through mode x and it is based on historical data, and S is the severity of the hazard, which is the expected level of harm to a human exposed to CO₂ release.

A set of hole sizes is explored here, from 6 mm to full bore rupture. The probability of the occurrence of each fracture hole is assumed as a distribution of the values shown in Table 7 in the next section. The dispersion has been modelled using the software ALOHA® (Areal Locations of Hazardous Atmospheres) and a description of the assumption is given in the next paragraph. For simplicity, the severity factor, S , is set to 1 in this study, i.e. assuming fatal consequence for an individual exposed to the CO₂ cloud.

6.2 FAILURE MODES AND PROBABILITY OF FAILURE

When dealing with multimodal transport of CO₂, several failure modes, unique to the different modes of transportation, must be considered when assessing the risks. Typical failure modes include corrosion, mechanical and material defects or damage and operational errors. In case of vessels transportation, accidents must be taken in consideration as well, which are the main cause of failure. Other failure modes, such as thermal stress could be relevant for low temperature transport in tanks, however it was neglected in this study as strategies to minimize thermal stress exist and are effective. In particular, it is assumed that the tank is never completely emptied, while a portion of cold gas is left inside to avoid drastic changes in internal temperature.

Internal corrosion is strongly dependent on impurities in CO₂ such as water, hydrogen sulfide or oxygen, and research in this field, with the aim to mitigate the risks, is becoming increasingly popular (Yan, et al.).

The probability of failure is also unique to the mode of transport, and historic data related to failure episodes must be collected for each failure mode. In general, the failure rate is calculated as:

$$\text{Failure rate} = \frac{\text{Number of failures}}{\text{Time} * \text{Length} * \text{Number of Vessels}} \quad (27)$$

The probability is then calculated as a function of the failure rate and the time (e.g., years) of operation of the equipment and the length (or distance) considered in the case study, following a common approach in reliability engineering (O'Connor, et al., 2011):

$$Probability = 1 - e^{-Failure\ rate * Time * Length * Number\ of\ Vessels} \quad (28)$$

where the *Number of Vessels* is only relevant when the mode of transportation is trucks, ships or trains, and for trains it refers to the number of tank cars employed for the specific case study.

Table 5 shows the failure rates for selected failure modes specific of the different transportation modes calculated based on several accessible sources including statistical analysis and public records.

Failure frequency for pipelines has been calculated by (Vitali, et al., 2022) as an average of 3.76×10^{-4} events/year based on an analysis of the Pipeline and Hazardous Materials Safety Administration (PHMSA) incident data related to CO₂ pipelines operating in the US from 1994 to 2021. They also categorize the failure mode and calculate the percentage contribution of each to the total failure frequency. In this work we calculate the failure frequency of each failure mode based on their analysis.

For trucks, accident data were gathered from data provided by the Federal Motor Carrier Safety Administration (FMCSA) for 2020-2022. The stats for accidents are comprehensive of Structural Failures and Operational Errors. For ships, historical data covering accident occurred between 2014 to 2022 reported by European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA, 2023) for cargo ships, where used here. The data include accidents due to operational failures, structural integrity and collisions. The average distance travelled was calculated based on data reported in the 2020 Annual Report on CO₂ Emissions from Maritime Transport from the European commission (EC, 2021).

The data for rail derailments, caused by a number of different reasons, including structural and operational failures, is expressed rather than in terms of number of trains, in terms of tonnes of cargo transported. The statistical data, relevant for Europe, have been extracted by the summary report of the D-Rail project (Robinson, et al., 2011).

TABLE 5. Historical data and Failure rates calculated for different modes of transportation.

PIPELINES	Corrosion	Equipment Failure	Mechanical Damage	Material Defects
Failures %	10.62	46.02	15.04	19.47
Total Failure Frequency	3.74×10^{-4}			
Failure Rate	3.97×10^{-5}	1.72×10^{-4}	5.62×10^{-5}	7.28×10^{-5}

TRUCKS	Traffic Accidents	SHIPS	Maritime Accidents
Failures	85,744	Failures	23,814
Time (years)	3	Time (years)	9
Length (km)	5,853,276.8	Length (km)	3,760,7124
Vessels	46712	Vessels	26,108
Failure Rate	1.05×10^{-7}	Failure Rate	2.69×10^{-9}

TRAINS	Derailments
Failures	157

Time (years)	6
Length (km)	1
Transported cargo (Mt/km)	2,142,622
Failures Rate	1.22×10⁻⁵

6.3 CONSEQUENCE ANALYSIS

For the consequence analysis, the dispersion of CO₂ has been computed using the ALOHA® software, which uses dispersion models to estimate the release of a chemical escaping from a tank or gas pipeline and form a hazardous gas cloud. ALOHA® generates a threat zone, which is the area where the cloud is predicted to exceed a user-specified concentration. The concentration of CO₂ chosen in these calculations is 40,000 ppm, identified as immediately dangerous to life (NIOSH, 1994). This choice is supported by the choice of assuming a high level of severity in the calculations.

The release is calculated using different hole sizes, for which a hypothetical probability of distribution has been assumed in this study, and it depends on the size of the vessel or the diameter of the pipeline, as well as on the pressure and atmospheric conditions of temperature and wind. The atmospheric conditions are project sensitive as they are dependent on the geographical area. Databases such as The Global Wind Atlas and the Trading Economics can be used to identify mean values for wind and temperature respectively. In the examples shown below in Tables 5.2 and 5.3 the average values are 3.7 m/s and 14.5°C, typical of the north of Italy. The size of the tanks for each mode of transportation has been chosen assuming standard measurements, but the number of tanks used in the calculations will be dependent on the case study. Trucks capacity is considered 38 tons, in line with assumptions and calculations used for the economic and environmental criteria, while tanks used in ships are based on a capacity of 2000 m³ carrying 2500 tons CO₂. For trains, a 50 tons capacity is assumed in the calculations. For pipeline transportation, threat area have been generated for gas phase pipelines suitable for transportation of small amounts of CO₂, nominally 60 kt/y, and for bigger amounts of 1 Mt/y. while the dense phase transportation via pipelines was modelled using the tank model since ALOHA® cannot handle liquid phase transport in the pipelines section, and the diameter indicated is suitable for a project transporting 1 Mt/y. The length of the segment is fixed at 30 km, assuming the presence of valves aimed at isolate the segment in case of a release. Table 5.2 and Table 5.3 show the input assumptions and the areas generated by the program.

TABLE 6. Input data used in ALHA for dispersion calculations for different modes of transportation.

Mode of Transport	Transport Pressure (bar)	Transport Temperature (bar)	Internal diameter (m)	Length of (m)
Pipeline Gas phase (60 kt)	35	15	1.1	30,000
Pipeline Gas phase (1 Mt/y)	35	15	3.2	30,000
Pipeline Dense phase	130	15	2.7	30,000
Truck 7 bar	7	-50	2.05	10
Truck 19 bar	19	-30	2.14	10
Ships 7 bar	7	-50	16.64	10
Ship 15 bar	15	-30	16.50	11
Trains	19	-30	2.45	10

TABLE 7. Threat areas generated with ALOHA for different modes of transportation and puncture hole with assumed probability of occurrence.

Puncture hole (cm)	Probability of puncture (%)	Threat Area (m ²)							
		Pipelines Gas 60 kt/y	Pipelines Gas 1 Mt/y	Pipelines Dense	Trucks 7 bar	Trucks 19 bar	Ships 7 bar	Ships 15 bar	Trains
0.6	40%	100	100	289	121	121	121	121	121
5	30%	-	-	-	7,569	10,816	10,201	14,161	13,689
14	20%	-	-	-	82,944	117,649	108,241	156,816	138,384
Full bore	10%	121	441	5184	145,924	144,400	6,760,000	5,760,000	270,400

7 MULTI-CRITERIA OPTIMIZATION

7.1 Objectives and advantages of multi-criteria optimization

Multi-criteria optimization is a type of optimization that involves balancing two or more conflicting objective functions. Unlike single-criteria optimization, which focuses on a single goal, such as minimizing cost or maximizing efficiency, multi-criteria optimization seeks to find a balance between several competing goals. The primary goal of multi-criteria optimization is to find a set of solutions, known as Pareto-optimal solutions, where no objective can be improved without worsening at least one other objective. This allows decision-makers to evaluate trade-offs and choose solutions that best meet their needs across multiple criteria.

The key advantages of the multi-objective optimization can be summarised as follows:

- (i) It provides a framework for considering multiple aspects of a problem, enabling more informed and balanced decisions.
- (ii) By presenting a range of Pareto-optimal solutions, it allows decision-makers to choose based on their preferences or priorities at the time.
- (iii) Many real-world problems involve conflicting objectives, and multi-objective optimization reflects this complexity, leading to solutions that are more applicable in practice.
- (iv) It allows for the exploration of trade-offs between competing objectives, which is critical for making well-rounded decisions in complex scenarios.

7.2 The multi-objective optimization model

A multi-objective optimization problem can be generally formulated as

$$\text{Minimize } F(\mathbf{x}) = [f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_k(\mathbf{x})], \quad (29)$$

subject to:

$$g_i(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0, \quad i=1, 2, \dots, m$$

$$h_j(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad i=1, 2, \dots, p$$

where $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ is the vector of decision variables, $F(\mathbf{x})$ is the vector of objective functions, $g_i(\mathbf{x})$ and $h_j(\mathbf{x})$ are inequality and equality constraints, respectively.

In the example of CO₂ multimodal transportation network, the objective functions in multi-criteria optimization include minimizing transportation costs, minimizing transportation risks, maximizing system reliability, minimizing the environmental impact of transportation, minimizing financial risks, maximizing societal benefits, and even considering the urgency of system implementation. Among all of these criteria, the cost, safety and environmental impact factors are the three major criteria commonly considered along with the cost in the decision-making (Becattini, et al., 2022). The decision variables in multi-objective optimization include the installation size of each transportation mode, the actual transportation flow for each mode, the interim and final amount of CO₂ stored, as well as the operational lifespan of each transportation mode.

To solve the multi-criteria optimization problem, one approach is the weighted sum method, where multiple objectives are combined into a single objective function:

$$\text{Minimize } W(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^k \omega_i f_i(\mathbf{x}), \quad (30)$$

where ω_i are the weights assigned to each objective function $f_i(\mathbf{x})$, reflecting their relative importance.

Another commonly used approach is to calculate the Pareto optimality and generate the Pareto Front from the Pareto-optimal solutions. A solution \mathbf{x}^* is said to be Pareto optimal if there is no other solution \mathbf{x} such that:

$$f_i(\mathbf{x}) \leq f_i(\mathbf{x}^*) \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}, \quad (31)$$

and

$$f_j(\mathbf{x}) < f_j(\mathbf{x}^*) \quad \text{for at least one } j \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}. \quad (32)$$

The Pareto Front is the set of all Pareto-optimal solutions, representing the trade-offs between the different objectives. Mathematically, the Pareto Front PF is defined as:

$$PF = \{F(\mathbf{x}) \mid \mathbf{x} \text{ is Pareto optimal}\}. \quad (33)$$

The Pareto Front provides a visual or conceptual representation of the best possible trade-offs among the objectives. In the objective function space, the Pareto Front often forms a curve (2D for two objectives) or a surface (3D for three objectives), where each point on the front corresponds to a different Pareto-optimal solution. For example, if we choose to minimize transportation costs and minimize the environmental impact of transportation, the curve for the 2D Pareto Front can be presented in Figure 6.

The circle points in Figure 6 represent feasible choices, and smaller values are preferred to larger ones. The red line presents the Pareto Front. Solutions on the Pareto Front represent the optimal trade-offs between cost and environmental impact. Any movement along the Pareto Front would improve one objective but worsen the other. For example, the movement from point B to point A would improve the environmental impact but worsen the cost.

FIGURE 6. Pareto Front for two objectives—minimum cost and minimum environmental impact.

However, solutions not on the Pareto Front are dominated by at least one solution on the front, meaning there is another solution that is better in at least one objective without being worse in the other. For example, point C is not at the Pareto Front because there is point B that is better in environmental impact but not making the cost worse.

Similarly, we can add one more objective variable for the risk impact in Figure 7 to produce a 3D Pareto Front. As shown in Figure 7, the Pareto Front in the 3D plot forms a surface. All solutions on this surface are non-dominated by each other, meaning that none of these solutions is superior to another in all objectives. The constructed Pareto Front will include a set of optimal solutions for multimodal transportation, balancing the transportation costs against the environmental impacts and risk impacts.

As explained in Section 2, to limit the number of input cases for the multi-objective optimization, several candidate transportation solutions will be identified first using the MILP model to meet the target transportation costs. This will be followed by optimizing the selected solutions against other objectives and constructing the Pareto fronts for the optimal solutions.

FIGURE 7. Pareto Front for three objectives—minimum cost, minimum environmental impact, and minimum risk.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This report describes a comprehensive methodology developed for the multi-criteria optimization of CO₂ transport chains, balancing the cost, environmental impact and safety factors. Given the importance of a number of factors for the investment decisions on CO₂ transport solutions, this methodology would be particularly useful for optimal planning of the CO₂ transport infrastructure roll-out in the future Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) cluster projects. The proposed methodology integrates the Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model of cost-based optimization of multi-modal CO₂ transport network involving pipelines, ships, trucks, and trains, and the multi-objective optimization approach that enables fine-tuning the decision-making accounting for non-economic factors of CO₂ transport.

The developed MILP model was coded and verified for simple CO₂ transportation networks scenarios, for which the optimal network configurations were pre-defined. The multi-objective optimization method was implemented to balance the cost and environmental impacts of CO₂ transport using pipelines and ships. The method was used to determine the hierarchy of optimal choice of modes for CO₂ transport within a realistic industrial cluster (Hennequin, 2024).

The developed methodology will be applied in WP5 to determine optimal multimodal transport solutions for CO₂ captured from the CaLby2030 demonstration plants, paving the way for the rollout of efficient and environmentally responsible CO₂ transport infrastructure.

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